

Quanti Farm

**CROP FARMING DATSs
FARM MANAGEMENT
INFORMATION SYSTEMS &
DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEMS**

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FACTSHEET #12

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WHAT ARE THE DATSs?

Digital Agricultural Technology Solutions (DATSs) are digital tools, systems, and platforms that collect, analyse, and use data to improve **farm management, productivity, sustainability, and animal welfare**.

They support better decision-making by turning **real-time information** into **targeted actions** on the farm.

WHAT ARE FARM MANAGEMENT INFORMATION SYSTEMS (FMIS) AND DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEMS (DSS)?

Farm Management Information Systems (FMIS) and Decision Support Systems (DSS) are a category of Crop Farming DATSs that combine farm data into a single decision platform. They help farmers **organise, store, and analyse information** related to crop production, costs, inputs, and farm activities, supporting both day-to-day and strategic decisions.

Their purpose is to **bring all relevant farm information together** and transform it into **useful recommendations and insights** for better crop management.

WHO IS IT FOR?

FMIS and DSS are designed for:

Crop Farmers and Farm Managers

seeking structured and data-driven decision support

Advisers and Extension Services

supporting farm planning and management

Agricultural Consultants and Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs)

promoting integrated digital tools

Researchers and Stakeholders

analysing digital farm management practices

They are suitable for **different crop types, farm sizes, and production systems.**

KEY OBJECTIVES

To support informed and timely farm management decisions

To improve productivity and operational efficiency

To reduce costs and operational risks

To support environmental sustainability and resource-efficient farming

To enable evidence-based crop management and planning

MAIN FEATURES

Farm Management Information Systems (FMIS)
and Decision Support Systems (DSS)
focus on integrating and analysing farm data:

Digital farm management platforms

Web-based platforms or smartphone applications that organise and manage farm information in one place.

Digital farm logs and record-keeping

Tools that record field operations, inputs, and activities, supporting planning, monitoring, and compliance.

Decision support and cost–benefit tools

Applications that analyse farm data and provide recommendations or economic insights to support decisions

Traceability systems

Digital systems that document production processes and inputs, supporting transparency and traceability.

Together, these tools help farmers **keep track of data, plan activities more efficiently, and make better-informed decisions**, supporting sustainable and resilient crop farming.

Learn
More

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